

The FEBI UIN SU Management Study Group Research Group's scientific research has become a reference worldwide.

The Bachelor of Management Study Program is a young study program at the **Universitas Islam Negeri Sumatera Utara** (UIN SU) of Medan) and officially obtained permission to open the study program on March 19, 2018 from the Indonesian Ministry of Research, Technology and Higher Education. The Bachelor of Management Study Program has played a role in various academic and non-academic accomplishments in a short period of time.

As a study program that prioritizes scientific development, the Bachelor of Management Study Program at UIN SU Medan continues to encourage the academic community, both lecturers and students, to continue to develop knowledge in the field of management and scientific publications.

As an effort to accommodate the academic community of the Bachelor of Management Study Program in developing knowledge, the Head of the Study Program of the Bachelor of Management Study Program at that time was Mr. Dr. **Muhammad Irwan Padli Nasution**, S.T., MM., M.Kom together with the Study Program Secretary, Mrs. Dr. Nurbaiti, M.Kom founded a research group known as the **Management Research Forum (MRF)** and appointed Mrs. Siti Aisyah, M.M, who is a permanent lecturer at the Bachelor of Management Study Program as its chairman. The MRF was officially opened on January 16, 2020 by Prof. Dr. Andri Soemitra, MA, who is also the Dean of the Faculty of Economics and Islamic Business (FEBI) at UIN SU.

MRF has carried out various activities, starting from regular discussions with lecturers in the Bachelor of Management Study Program, Faculty of Islamic Economics and Business, as well as with lecturers from various universities in Indonesia. MRF is also a forum for lecturers and students to develop research ideas and publish scientific articles. Together with MRF, the Bachelor of Management Study Program is consistently ranked among the Top 5 Publication Performance Study Programs at UIN SU Medan.

MRF Research Group Researcher, Dr. Muhammad Irwan Padli Nasution, S.T., MM., M.Kom, Dr. Nurbaiti, M. Kom, Dr. Nurlaila, Dr. Tri Ina Nur Fadila Rahma, M.E.I and Dr. Kamila, MA, has presented the results of her research at the International Conference, namely "3rd International Conference on Computer and Informatics Engineering (IC2IE), 15-16 Sept. 2020". The scientific articles presented were then published in Scopus indexed Proceedings published by IEEE Publisher.

The article by MRF researchers entitled "**Face Recognition Login Authentication for Digital Payment Solution at COVID-19 Pandemic**", has now been cited and has become a reference for international researchers (there have been 11 SCOPUS papers cited so far) details at URL:

<https://plu.mx/plum/a/?doi=10.1109%2Fic2ie50715.2020.9274654>

plu.mx/plum/a/?doi=10.1109%2Fic2ie50715.2020.9274654

Face Recognition Login Authentication for Digital Payment Solution at COVID-19 Pandemic

Citation Data: 2020 3rd International Conference on Computer and Informatics Engineering, IC2IE 2020, Page: 48-51

Publication Year: 2020

Metrics Details	
CITATIONS	11
Citation Indexes	11
Scopus ↗	11
CrossRef	5
CAPTURES	122
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Mendeley ↗	122

Conference Paper Description

On March 11, 2020 the World Health Organization has announced the status of a global pandemic of corona virus disease 2019 or also called corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19). The World Health Organization defines this disease as a pandemic because all citizens of the world are potentially exposed to COVID-19 infection. With the establishment of the global pandemic status, WHO also confirmed that COVID-19 was an international emergency. The trend of digitalization is becoming a new business trend to develop and survive in the midst of a crisis due to this pandemic. The online buying and selling market, digital payments and electronic health services, from online training classes to consulting with doctors via the internet, continue to increase. Some companies in the offline market also continue to operate by implementing health protocols. The form of digital payments continues increasing, this is because according to WHO the surface of objects can be a medium in the spread of the covid-19 virus. However, some digital payment methods require users to scan a QR code and enter a Personal Identification Number (PIN) in the Electronic Data Capture machine. [Show more](#)

Bibliographic Details

DOI: [10.1109/ic2ie50715.2020.9274654](https://doi.org/10.1109/ic2ie50715.2020.9274654) ↗

URL ID: <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?partnerID=HzOxMe3b&scp=85098932902&origin=inward> ↗; <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ic2ie50715.2020.9274654> ↗; <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9274654/> ↗

AUTHOR(S):
Muhammad Irwan Padli Nasution; Nurbaiti Nurbaiti; Nurlaila Nurlaila; Tri Ina Fadila Rahma; Kamilah Kamilah

PUBLISHER(S):
Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)

TAG(S):
Business, Management and Accounting; Computer Science; Decision Sciences [Show less](#)

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In 2024 the scientific article by Dr. Muhammad Irwan Padli Nasution, S.T., M.M., M.Kom, et al. The paper cited by researchers Yang, T., Gu, F in their research entitled "Overview of modulation techniques for spatially structured-light 3D imaging" which was published in the Journal of Optics and Laser Technology. The Optics and Laser Technology Journal is a journal published by Elsevier Publisher which has been **indexed in Scopus since 1970**, with SJR 0.874 (SCOPUS Q1).

11 documents have cited:

Face Recognition Login Authentication for Digital Payment Solution at COVID-19 Pandemic
 Nasution M.I.P., Nurbaiti N., Nurlaila N., Rahma T.I.F., Kamilah K.
 (2020) *2020 3rd International Conference on Computer and Informatics Engineering, IC2IE 2020*, art. no. 9274654, pp. 48-51.

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- Green (1) >
- (1) >

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Document title	Authors	Year	Source	Cited by
1 Overview of modulation techniques for spatially structured-light 3D imaging View abstract Related documents	Yang, T., Gu, F.	2024	Optics and Laser Technology	5
2 Biometric Authentication Model Based on Transformation of Face Image into a PIN Number Usable During the Covid-19 Pandemic	BADOVINAC, N., SIMIC, D.	2023	Romanian Journal of Information Science and Technology	0

Source details

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Optics and Laser Technology

Formerly known as: Optics Technology

Scopus coverage years: from 1970 to Present

Publisher: Elsevier

ISSN: 0030-3992

Subject area: [Engineering: Electrical and Electronic Engineering](#) [Materials Science: Electronic, Optical and Magnetic Materials](#)
[Physics and Astronomy: Atomic and Molecular Physics, and Optics](#)

Source type: Journal

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CiteScore 2022	8.3
SJR 2022	0.874
SNIP 2022	1.577

CiteScore CiteScore rank & trend Scopus content coverage

CiteScore rank 2022 In category: Electrical and Electronic Engin...

Rank	Source title	CiteScore 2022	Percentile
#102	Optics and Laser Technology	8.3	86th percentile
#1	IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials	82.5	99th percentile
#2	Nature Nanotechnology	54.6	99th percentile
#3	Nature Electronics	38.3	99th percentile
#4	Nano-Micro Letters	32.6	99th percentile
#5	Proceedings of the IEEE	31.6	99th percentile
#6	Nano Energy	29.3	99th percentile

CiteScore trend

The scientific work of the FEBI UIN SU Bachelor of Management Study Program has been widely influential, making it one of the best academic achievements of the program globally. The MRF Research Group continues to work and is useful in contributing to academic development in Study Programs, Faculties and UIN SU. MRF has the potential to serve as an example, particularly at UIN SU, of a research group that is beneficial in scientific advancements.

Karya Kelompok Riset Prodi Manajemen FEBI UIN SU Jadi Rujukan International

Program Studi S1 Manajemen merupakan program studi muda yang ada pada Universitas Islam Negeri Sumatera Utara Medan (UIN SU Medan) dan resmi memperoleh izin pembukaan program studi pada tanggal 19 Maret 2018 dari Kementerian Riset, Teknologi dan Pendidikan Tinggi Indonesia. Program Studi S1 Manajemen dalam waktu singkat telah menyumbangkan berbagai prestasi akademik maupun non akademik.

Sebagai program studi yang mengedepankan perkembangan keilmuan, Program Studi S1 Manajemen UIN SU Medan terus mendorong para civitas akademiknya, baik dosen maupun mahasiswa untuk terus mengembangkan dalam keilmuan bidang manajemen dan publikasi ilmiahnya. Sebagai upaya dalam mewadahi civitas akademika Program Studi S1 Manajemen dalam mengembangkan keilmuan, Ketua Program Studi Program Studi S1 Manajemen pada waktu itu adalah Bapak Dr. Muhammad Irwan Padli Nasution, S.T., MM., M.Kom bersama Sekretaris Program Studi, Ibu Dr. Nurbaiti, M.Kom mendirikan grup riset yang dikenal dengan nama *Management Research Forum* (MRF) dan menunjuk Ibu Siti Aisyah, M.M yang merupakan dosen tetap Program Studi S1 Manajemen sebagai ketuanya. *Management Research Forum* (MRF) diresmikan pada tanggal 16 Januari 2020 oleh Dekan Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Islam UIN SU, Bapak Prof. Dr. Andri Soemitra, MA.

Berbagai kegiatan telah dilaksanakan oleh MRF mulai dari diskusi rutin bersama dosen di lingkup Program Studi S1 Manajemen, Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Islam (FEBI), maupun bersama para dosen dari berbagai Universitas di Indonesia. MRF juga menjadi wadah bagi para dosen dan mahasiswa untuk mengembangkan ide-ide penelitian dan publikasi artikel ilmiah. Bersama MRF, Program Studi S1 Manajemen selalu berada dalam peringkat Top 5 Kinerja Publikasi Program Studi di lingkungan UIN SU Medan.

Peneliti Kelompok Riset MRF, Dr. Muhammad Irwan Padli Nasution, S.T., MM., M.Kom, Dr. Nurbaiti, M.Kom, Dr. Nurlaila, Dr. Tri Inda Nur Fadila Rahma, M.E.I dan Dr. Kamila, MA, telah mempresentasikan hasil penelitiannya pada International Conference yaitu "[3rd International Conference on Computer and Informatics Engineering \(IC2IE\)](#), 15-16 Sept. 2020". Artikel ilmiah yang dipresentasikan tersebut kemudian dipublikasikan pada Proceeding terindeks Scopus yang diterbitkan oleh IEEE Publisher. Artikel karya peneliti MRF tersebut berjudul "[Face Recognition Login Authentication for Digital Payment Solution at COVID-19 Pandemic](#)", saat ini telah disitasi dan menjadi referensi bagi peneliti

international (sampai saat ini disitasi 11 paper SCOPUS), detail pada URL: <https://plu.mx/plum/a/?doi=10.1109%2Fic2ie50715.2020.9274654>

The screenshot shows the Scopus interface. At the top, it states "11 documents have cited:" followed by the article title "Face Recognition Login Authentication for Digital Payment Solution at COVID-19 Pandemic" by Nasution M.I.P., Nurbaiti N., Nurlaila N., Rahma T.I.F., Kamilah K. (2020) 2020 3rd International Conference on Computer and Informatics Engineering, IC2IE 2020, art. no. 9274654, pp. 48-51.

The search results table is as follows:

Document title	Authors	Year	Source	Cited by
1. Overview of modulation techniques for spatially structured-light 3D imaging	Yang, T., Gu, F.	2024	Optics and Laser Technology 169,110037	4

The "Source details" section for "Optics and Laser Technology" shows a CiteScore of 8.3 for 2022 and an SJR of 0.874. The CiteScore rank is 758 out of 8102 journals in the category "Electrical and Electronic Engineering". A CiteScore trend chart shows an upward trend from 2018 to 2022.

Year	CiteScore value	Percentile in category
2018	~2.5	~80th
2019	~3.0	~85th
2020	~3.5	~90th
2021	~4.0	~95th
2022	8.3	~99th

Pada tahun 2024 artikel ilmiah karya Dr. Muhammad Irwan Padli Nasution, S.T., M.M., M.Kom, dkk. tersebut disitasi oleh peneliti Yang, T., Gu, F pada penelitiannya yang berjudul [“Overview of modulation techniques for spatially structured-light 3D imaging”](#) yang dipublikasikan pada [Jurnal Optics and Laser Technology](#). Jurnal Optics and Laser Technology merupakan jurnal diterbitkan Elsevier Publisher yang telah terindeks pada Scopus sejak tahun 1970, dengan SJR 0.874 (Q1).

Hal ini menjadi salah satu prestasi akademik yang gemilang bagi Program Studi S1 Manajemen FEBI UIN SU di Internasional karena karya ilmiahnya telah berdampak luas pada Internasional. Kelompok Riset MRF terus berkarya dan bermanfaat untuk turut berkontribusi dalam mengembangkan akademik pada Program Studi, Fakultas maupun UIN SU. Semoga MRF dapat menjadi contoh khususnya pada UIN SU sebagai kelompok Riset yang bermanfaat dalam pengembangan keilmuan. (Humas MRF)